

Bidirectional People Counters as a Catalyst for Smart Cities in the Technological Singularity Era

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Abstract: Bidirectional people counting, a key feature of smart cities, tracks individuals entering and exiting doorways while monitoring their direction of movement. In the Technological Singularity era, emerging technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI) and digital binary systems optimize efficiency, conserving time and energy. This study examines the Count-it People Counter, which uses infrared beam disruption to detect movement. The system transmits and receives infrared signals, incrementing count values upon beam interruption. Users select the desired count direction. This research investigates the benefits, drawbacks, and implementation strategies of bidirectional visitor counters, exploring: advantages, challenges, and Implementation. By analyzing the effectiveness and limitations of bidirectional people counting systems, this study contributes to the development of efficient, AI-driven smart city infrastructure.

Index Terms - Bidirectional people counting, Smart Cities, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Technological Singularity, Arduino, infrared technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Bidirectional Visitor Counter with an Automatic Room Light Controller is a reliable circuit design that takes over the chore of monitoring the gate and room lights as well as counting the number of visitors entering the room quite correctly. If a person enters the room, this counter is incremented by one value, and the light in the room is automatically switched on. At the same time, if someone leaves the room, this counter is decremented by one value, and the light in the room is automatically switched off. This has so far been achieved due to the technological singularity brought by emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), robotics, digital binary systems, and Internet of Things (IoT), among others [13]. On the LCD screens, the total number of people entering and leaving the room is also seen and displayed. The above task is performed and controlled by a microcontroller. It receives signals from sensors, and this signal is controlled by Arduino software (IDE). This is one of the characteristics of a smart city in which digital identity is key in order to ensure the security and safety of the system [14]. Also, the total number of people in the room, whether incremented or decremented, will still be reflected in the LCD, making this device very user friendly.

Fig. 1: A model of Bi-directional Peoples Counter

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In [1], this research is designed and presented to count the number of visitors entering an auditorium, hall, offices, malls, sports venues, and houses. This system tracks both entering and exiting visitors to the auditorium, hall, or other location where it is installed. The system automatically identifies the visitor's entry and exit based on the interruption of the infrared ray sensors. If the system is successfully implemented, it displays the number of visitors present in the auditorium or hall that have entered. When used in places where visitors must be counted and controlled, the system is cost-effective. The counting of visitors can be time-consuming, so it helps to maximize employee efficiency and effectiveness, time savings, and an organization's sales potential, among other things. In [2], demand for electricity, and also improved security and save time. These are critical towards achieving a smart city through the technological singularity era approach [15]. As the technology improvements preponderate in today's digital world, we prefer classier and smarter developments in simple and basic needs of human lives, so this paper gives us a solution to make the surroundings economic and smarter. To achieve this objective, we can install automatic room monitoring in every institution, industry, organization, hall, and house. This design uses infrared ray sensors to detect the persons entering and leaving the room and monitors the room appliances like fans, lights, and air conditioners. Developing and generating electricity on a small scale is a cumbersome process; instead, we consume less electricity and conserve it for sustainable development of energy resources. The proposed archetypal from the paper can control and monitor the room appliances respective to the people in the room; additionally, it can also immediately count the number of persons in a room. It has various applications in the field of consuming energy resources and also as a bi-directional visitor counter. The author in [3], This paper is "Automated light controller with visitor counter system" is a reliable circuit that is controlling the room lights with counting the number of persons or visitors in the room. If anybody or someone enters the room, the counter will be incremented, and the light in the room will be switched ON if the person or anyone leaves or comes out of the room or place the device is installed, then this counter is incremented. The light will be switched off until all the persons or visitors leave the room. The number of persons or visitors inside the room is displayed on the LCD. The microcontroller does this work. It receives the signals from the IR sensors, and this signal is operated under the control of source code, which is stored in the microcontroller. The microcontroller atmega328 continuously monitors the infrared sensor since it is the brain of the system. When any object passes or interrupts, the IR sensor signal is sent to the microcontroller, and the result is displayed on the LCD. In [4], this research describes a circuit that is used for monitoring the room lights according to the count of persons in the room and instantaneously works as a security system when the camera is attached. When somebody enters the room, then the counter will be incremented accordingly, the LED light in the room will be switched on, and when anyone leaves the room, then the counter will be decreased. The light will only be switched off when the room is vacant. The number of LED lights will be ON according to the total number of persons inside the room, and the count will be displayed. The author [5] in this research, the congestion control Bidirectional A digital visitor counter is a consistent circuit design that is mostly designed to monitor the room appliances as well as to count the number of people or individuals entering the arena very precisely and likewise avoid overcrowding in the different areas of usage. When a person enters the arena, a counter is maintained for presenting the number of people and is updated by one, and the appliances in the arena will be turned ON when a person leaves the arena. The counter is maintained for presenting the number of

people and is decreased by one. The appliances will turn off when all the people in the arena go out. The overall count of people inside the arena will be presented on the LCD. When a particle passes through the infrared receivers, then the infrared rays falling on the receivers are obstructed. This obstruction is sensed by the microcontroller. It also can manage fans based on the relay provided. If the room reaches the maximum capacity, then, by using a Wi-Fi module, a message is sent to authorities to limit the person entering the room. Thereby congestion is avoided. In [6], in this digital world, the use of technology is very advanced, and we prefer things to be done automatically without any human effort. This research likewise aids in decreasing human efforts. Likewise, it is very useful to conserve resources. In today's world, there is a continuous need for automatic appliances. With the increase in the standard of living, there is a sense of urgency for developing circuits that would ease the complexity of life. Also, if at all one wants to know the number of people present in the room so as not to have congestion, this circuit proves to be helpful. An automatic room light controller with a visitor counter is a reliable circuit that takes over the task of controlling the room lights as well as counting the number of persons and visitors in the room very precisely. The author in [7], this, paper presents the design and construction of a digital bidirectional visitor counter (DBVC). The DBVC is a dependable circuit that takes over the task of counting the number of persons and visitors in the room very precisely and beeps a warning alarm when the number of visitors exceeds the capacity limit of the auditorium or hall. When somebody enters the room, then the counter is incremented by one (+1), and when anyone leaves the room, then the counter is decremented by one (-1). The total number of persons inside the room is also displayed on the LCD (Liquid Crystal Display). The microcontroller is used for detecting an entry or exit action and computing the figures (addition and subtraction) to acquire accurate results. It receives the signals from the sensors, and this signal is operated under the control of embedded programming code, which is stored in the ROM of the microcontroller. The microcontroller continuously monitors the infrared receivers. When any object passes through the IR receivers, then the IR rays falling on the receivers are obstructed. The obstruction occurs under two circumstances: either you obstruct sensor 1 (i.e., outside the building) before sensor 2 (i.e., which is inside the building); this shows that you are entering the building, or you do it the other way around, which is obstructing sensor 2 before sensor 1 to indicate an exit movement. This obstruction is sensed by the microcontroller, computed, and displayed by a 16x2 LCD screen. The author in [8], a Study on the Impact and Challenges of Temperature Detection System.

III. ACHIEVING SMART CITY BENEFITS OF BIDIRECTIONAL PEOPLE COUNTERS

1. Measuring conversion rates accurately:

One of the most fundamental retail business metrics is to know what proportion of customers enter a store and leave with something. Retailers can track conversion rates in greater detail by using bidirectional people counters, which can determine how many people are entering and leaving a store at any given time. This allows retailers to see how different factors, like the time of day, store traffic, and the number of sales associates and cashiers on duty, affect conversion rates.

2. Keeping an ongoing count of the number of people in a location:

One way to find out how many people are in a store from the beginning of the business day until closing is to use a bidirectional people counter. This is important because it allows conversion rate data to be collected that is related to specific events or periods of the day, rather than the more meaningless daily or weekly averages. Retailers may ascertain the ideal client count in a particular area by tracking changes in overall population numbers. More traffic is generally a positive thing, but too much of it can be detrimental. For example, an excessive number of customers might result in packed aisles, a shortage of employees to serve them, and a higher chance of out-of-stock situations.

3. Deploying staff more effectively:

It's crucial to understand not only the total number of workers required at any given moment in larger retail sites with several departments, but also the areas where those workers will have the greatest influence on sales and customer service. This becomes a challenging undertaking in the absence of bidirectional people's capacity to track traffic flows and identify patterns of density. For instance, a department with high traffic density that does not see a rise in sales of its products may not have enough employees to handle customer service, especially in areas like jewelry, cosmetics, or home décor where high customer interaction is necessary.

4. Measuring marketing success:

Bidirectional people counters provide minute-by-minute, minute-by-minute data on total store counts, traffic patterns, and conversion rates that are essential for assessing the success of in-store promotions as well as large-scale marketing campaigns aimed at driving foot traffic. Basic business indicators that are valuable for analysis and comparisons to rivals' performance, other stores in a chain, and past campaigns, such as CPM (cost per thousand), sales per square foot, and the cost of reaching one thousand individuals or households, depend on correct data [10].

IV. DISADVANTAGES OF BIDIRECTIONAL PEOPLE COUNTERS

1. The research gets quite complicated if a room has more than one door.
2. If numerous persons enter at once, the infrared (IR) sensor will not be able to detect them [11].

V. THE FUNCTIONING OF THE ARDUINO BIDIRECTIONAL PEOPLE COUNTER

Two infrared (IR) sensors are used in the study to identify when people enter and leave a room. The IR sensors are positioned at each room's entrance or at the edge of the door. The project indicates the precise number of persons in the room as well as whether they are leaving or entering. An IR transmitter and an IR receiver make up the two components of an infrared sensor. An IR LED is another name for an IR transmitter, and a photodiode is another name for an IR receiver. As the name suggests, the IR transmitter emits infrared radiation, which the receiver records when the radiation strikes an obstruction and reflects back. The photodiode's resistance will change depending on how many reflected infrareds light it receives. There will be a voltage drop as a result. The Arduino makes use of this voltage variation. In summary, the voltage across the DATA pin will be near the GND pin if an object blocks the IR sensor. The voltage will be about 5V if there is no obstruction in the path of the infrared photons. Attach both IR sensors' VCC pins to the Arduino Uno's 5V pin. Attach both IR sensors' GND pins to the Arduino Uno's GND pin. Lastly, attach the IR sensors' DATA pins to pins 7 and 8, respectively, on the Arduino [12].

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, a unique architecture for an automated light controller, gate control, and bidirectional visitor counter is proposed and implemented in an economical manner. It describes how the gate control, the room light controller, and the bidirectional guest counter are powered by the microcontroller. This equipment is fairly inexpensive. This study uses inexpensive, store-bought supplies. Because of this, the net deployment cost is extremely low and within the means of the typical consumer, particularly in Africa. Because of the substantial spike in COVID-19, this low-cost plan aims to improve living conditions, make guest counting more difficult, and prevent unnecessary entry [9]. In this research, we have also spoken about the advantages and disadvantages of employing the bidirectional people's counters.

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